

ETHNOMEDICINAL PLANTS OF NATURAL SAL PATCH AT DONUBAI, PARVATHIPURAM MANYAM DISTRICT, AP, INDIA.

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ABSTRACT

While changing trends and increasing consciousness towards curing diseases, people are searching for natural remedies. In this perspective ethnomedicine is the best way to follow from ancient period. The denizens of Sal patch at Donubai use medicinal plants for getting relief from several ailments. Therefore, the present investigation pays attention on 107 medicinally important plant species belong to 96 genera of 46 families. Fabaceae is the predominant family with 14 species followed by Lamiaceae (6 spp.), Apocynaceae and Asteraceae (5 spp. each), Amaranthaceae, Malvaceae, Moraceae, Rutaceae and Zingiberaceae (4 species each), remaining families with one-three. The primitive tribes largely use herbs (40; 37.38%), trees (34; 31.77%) shrubs (26; 24.29%) and climbers (07; 6.54%).

Among the plant parts used by tribes in various formulations, the leaves are the most useful rather than roots, whole plant, stem bark, fruits, seeds, stem, rhizome and flowers. A total of 52 diseases can be cured by using 107 medicinal plants are for aches, rheumatism, problems of digestive system, excretory system, respiratory system, nervous system, gynecology & obstetrics, oral, skin related problems, fevers, stings and bites. Sometimes, as huge number of tourists visiting this area and their indiscriminate behavior, medicinal plants which are abundantly available are likely to become rare in future.

KEYWORDS: *Ethnomedicine, Donubai, Sal patch, Seethampetamandal, Medicinal plants, Parvathipuram Manyam*

INTRODUCTION

Hippocrates' quote, "Nature is the best physician," suggests that the body has an amazing ability to heal itself, and natural remedies or treatments often work best to aid in this process. It emphasizes the importance of living in harmony with nature and using its resources for health and well-being. For a long period of time, plants have been a valuable source of natural products for maintaining human health. The use of plant compounds for pharmaceutical purposes has gradually increased all over the world. According to World Health Organization medicinal plants would be the best source to obtain a variety of drugs. About 80% of individuals from developed and under developed countries use traditional medicine, which has compounds derived from medicinal plants. Therefore, such plants should be investigated for better understanding of the properties, safety, and efficiency ^[1]. Ethnomedicine emphasizes a holistic approach to health, considering not only physical symptoms but also social, spiritual, and environmental factors. This integrated perspective aligns with the growing recognition of the interconnectedness of fitness, addressing both the physical and psychosocial impacts of health crises like COVID-19.

Donubai region of Parvathipuram Manyam district is a very beautiful place which is rich in biodiversity and natural resources. Many primitive tribal people living near the Sal Forest of this area collect and use medicines for their primary health care. M. Sankara Rao (2010) and K. Aruna (2010) ^[2,3] worked for their doctoral degree on the ethnobotany of the district. G. Sailu *et al* (2013) published 41 medicinally important plants in Seethampeta mandal ^[4]. Against this backdrop, a study was undertaken to document the Ethnomedicinal knowledge of the primitive tribal people in and around natural Sal patch at Donubai.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study area is one of the natural sal patch lies between the 18.742714⁰ North latitude and 83.718368⁰ Eastern Longitude in Seethampeta mandal, Parvathipuram Manyam District of Andhra Pradesh state. Limits spread over an extent of 48.02 ha. and having 5.56 km. as its perimeter. Its sprawl over 4 bits in Burnakonda Reserve Forest Compartment Nos.210, 231 & 232 near to Donubai Village in Veeraghattam Section of Palakonda Range. The girth class of Sal plantation varies from 23 cm. to 103 cm. with height 7.00 m. to 15 m. Under the Sal trees hill Mango, Xylia, Terminalia,

Cashew, Citrus, and Bauhinia covered surface area ^[5]. Primitive tribal Groups like Savara, Jatapu and Gadabas are closely associated with this *Sal* Forest, they are dependent on the forest for their needs. Mainly they rely on plants for primary health care ^[6,7,8,9,10]. Hence the present work has been undertaken to make a survey to collect information on medicinal plants.

The methodology and mode of approach for ethnobotanical enumeration is adopted from the classical work of Jones (1941), Schultes (1954), Jain (1981a, b; 1987, 1989), Bellany (1993), Chadwick and Martin (1994) and Cotton (1996). The present study is the outcome of a series of intensive field studies conducted over a period of one year (2022-2023) in different seasons. Information was compiled through scientifically guided discussion, interviews and general conversations with herbal doctors, elderly people, cattle herders, Vana Samrakshana Samithi (VSS) members etc. The plants were identified with the help of local standard flora.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

During exploration trips, medicinally useful information has been recorded on 107 plant species belonging to 96 genera of 46 families, which are being potentially exploited by the tribes inhabited in and around Donubai natural *sal* patch. For each species the following ethnomedicinal information was provided i.e., species name, Local name, family name, kind of plant, and ethnomedicinal use (Table: 1). The floristic composition is dominated by higher plants (105) and less number of pteridophytes (2). They belong to 2 divisions, 4 classes, 3 sub classes, 14 series, 21 orders and 46 families. These families are distributed as dicotyledones-31 (polypetalae-15; gamopetalae-13; monochlamidae-3), monocotyledons 12 and 2 from pteridophytes. Family wise analysis of species revealed that the family Fabaceae is dominant one with 14 species followed by Lamiaceae (6), Apocynaceae and Asteraceae each one having 5, Amaranthaceae, Malvaceae, Moraceae, Rutaceae, Zingiberaceae having 4 species each, remaining families with one-three (Table: 2).

From the present study (Fig: 1) it is clear that the local people use herbs of 40 species (37.38%), trees 34 spp. (31.77%), shrubs 26 spp. (24.29%), and climbers 07 spp. (6.54%). Analysis of the plant parts used in different practices (Fig: 2) are as follows: Leaf 28 spp. (26.16%), root 21 spp. (19.62%), whole plant 11 spp. (10.28%), Stem bark 11 spp. (10.28%), fruit 10 spp. (9.34%), seed 10 spp. (9.34%) stem 6 spp.(5.60%), rhizome 4 spp. (3.73%), flower 2 spp. 1.6%, tuber 2 spp. (1.86%) endosperm 1 spp. (0.93%) and sprout 1 spp. (0.93%). is less percentage; Resin is the only secondary metabolites observe in these collections.

The collected curative practices are classified into fourteen categories such as: 10 species for aches and rheumatism, 9 spp. for problems of digestive system, 9 spp. for problems of excretory system, 4 spp. for fevers, 8 spp. for problems of respiratory system, 9 spp. for problems of gynecology & obstetrics, 19 spp. for skin related problems, 6 spp. for stings and bites, 7 spp. for oral health problems, 5 spp. for nervous disorders, 2 spp. for bone fractures, 4 spp. for life style diseases, 12 spp. for miscellaneous problems and another 2 plant species were also used for curing cattle diseases.

Table: 1. The botanical name, Local name, family name, kind of plant, and ethnomedicinal use of plant species from *Sal* patch at Donubai.

S. No	Botanical Name	Local Name	Family Name	Kind of Plant	Medicinal uses
1	<i>Achyranthus aspera</i> L.	Dakshinapulla	Amaranthaceae	Perennial herb	Stem is used as a tooth brush to clear pyorrhoea
2	<i>Adiantum caudatum</i> L.	Alipiribaddu	Pteridaceae	Herb	Juice of plant given with water for nervous debility.
3	<i>Aegle marmelos</i> (L.) Correa	Sriphalam	Rutaceae	Medium sized tree	Unripe fruit is used as a remedy for dysentery
4	<i>Agave sisalana</i> Perrine	Kittalamatta	Asperagaceae	Fleshy herb	Crushed root is given with milk to children for cough
5	<i>Ageratum conyzoides</i> L.	Nuguaku	Asteraceae	Herb	Juice of the plant is employed for eczema

6	<i>Ailanthus excelsa</i> Roxb.	Peddamanu	Simaroubaceae	Tree	Juice of the leaves is useful in gonorrhoea
7	<i>Albizia lebeck</i> (L.) Benth.	Dhirisena	Fabaceae	Tree	Stem bark inhaled to cure migraine
8	<i>Amaranthus spinosus</i> L.	Mulluthotakura	Amaranthaceae	Herb	Roots are useful in dyspepsia
9	<i>Amorphophallus paeoniifolius</i> (Dennst.) Nicolson	Adividumpa	Araceae	Stout herb	Plant paste is used for skin troubles
10	<i>Annona reticulate</i> L.	Rambalam	Annonaceae	Small tree	Fruit is laxative and used in abdominal pains
11	<i>Annona squamosa</i> L.	Sitaphalam	Annonaceae	Small tree	Seed oil is applied to remove white spots on skin
12	<i>Aristolochia bracteolate</i> Lam.	Gadidagadapa	Aristolochiaceae	prostrate herb	Leaf paste is mixed with neem oil and applied to eczema
13	<i>Aristolochia indica</i> L.	Nalleeswari	Aristolochiaceae	Shrubby twiners	The root is used to snake-bite
14	<i>Argyrea nervosa</i> (Burm.f.) Bojer	Chandrapodi	Convolvulaceae	Climbing shrub	Latex is applied to heal wounds
15	<i>Atlantia monophylla</i> DC.	Karunimma	Rutaceae	Shrub	Fruit oil is applied externally to cure paralysis
16	<i>Atrocarpus heterophyllus</i> Lam.	Panasa	Moraceae	Tree	Fruit peel decoction is taken to cure diabetes
17	<i>Azima tetracantha</i> Lam.	Uppikampa	Salvadoraceae	Bushy shrub	Leaf paste is applied to heal mastitis
18	<i>Bambusa bambos</i> (L.) Voss	Mullavedhuru	Poaceae	Shrub	Bamboo sprout paste applied externally to bone fractures
19	<i>Bidens biternata</i> (Lour.) Merr. & Sherff	Karrothi	Asteraceae	Herb	The juice of leaves is used to relieve ear-ache
20	<i>Bixa orellana</i> L.	Sindhura kaya	Bixaceae	Small tree	Fruit paste with black pepper powder taken for jaundice
21	<i>Boerhavia diffusa</i> L.	Ambalimadu	Nyctaginaceae	Procumbent herb	The root is used in the treatment of Asthma
22	<i>Bonnaya ciliate</i> (Colsm.) Sreng.	Maripikura	Linderniaceae	Herb	Decoction of leaves used for muscular pains
23	<i>Borassus flabellifer</i> L.	Thati	Arecaceae	Tall tree	Liquid endosperm used for Ichthyosis
24	<i>Cajanus scarabaeoides</i> (L.) Thouars	Teegaulava	Fabaceae	Twinning shrub	Roots are chewed to counter act on snake bite
25	<i>Calophyllum inophyllum</i> L.	Ponnachettu	Calophyllaceae	Tree	Root paste is applied externally to cure varicose veins
26	<i>Canavalia gladiata</i> (Jacq.) DC.	Karutamba	Fabaceae	Shrubby climber	Root powder is taken orally to deteriorate kidney stones

27	<i>Cardiospermum helicacabum</i> L.	Budda-kakara	Sapindaceae	Herbaceous climber	Juice of the crushed plant is said to be useful in improving appetite
28	<i>Cascabela thevetia</i> (L.) Lippold	Ganneru	Apocynaceae	Small tree	The root is chewed for relief of toothache
29	<i>Cassutha filiformis</i> L.	Seetammasavaram	Lauraceae	Twinning herb	The juice of the plant is used effectively for inflamed eyes
30	<i>Causonis trifolia</i> (L.) Mabb. & J.Wen	Kanputeega	Vitaceae	Climbing shrub	The plant ash is considered emmenagogue
31	<i>Celosia argentea</i> L.	Gulimikura	Amaranthaceae	Herb	Seeds powder with jaggery is taken for curing haematuria
32	<i>Centotheca lappacea</i> (L.) Desv.	Vedhurugaddi	Poaceae	Herb	Leaf paste applied for skin disease
33	<i>Cipadessa baccifera</i> (Roxb. ex Roth) Miq.	Randabilli	Poaceae	Shrub	Tender stem is used to cure pyorrhoea
34	<i>Cissampelos pareira</i> L.	Paterutivva	Menispermaceae	Twinning herb	Tuber tonic is used in bowel complaints
35	<i>Coccinia grandis</i> (L.) Voigt	Kakidonda	Cucurbitaceae	Herbaceous climber	Root paste is applied externally to cure piles
36	<i>Colocasia esculenta</i> (L.) Schott	Sarikanda	Araceae	Tuberous herb	Boiled corm eaten for irritable bowel syndrome
37	<i>Commelina benghalensis</i> L.	Kodukalu	Commelinaceae	Creeping herb	Roots are chewed for indigestion troubles
38	<i>Corchorus aestuans</i> L.	Nelabeera	Malvaceae	Herb	Leaves are used externally for scabies, itches and other skin diseases
39	<i>Cordia dichotoma</i> G. Forst.	Nakkirichettu	Boraginaceae	Tree	Bark powder with sesame oil is applied for rheumatism
40	<i>Crinum asiaticum</i> L.	Chalavadumpa	Amaryllidaceae	Herb	Fresh root paste is used to epilepsy
41	<i>Curcuma pseudomontana</i> J.Graham	Kondapasupu	Zingiberaceae	Herb	Rhizome paste is taken orally to cure menstrual problems
42	<i>Cyanthillium cinereum</i> (L.) H.Rob.	Sankarayyammokka	Asteraceae	Herb	Plant decoction is used as expectorant
43	<i>Dalbergia lanceolaria</i> L.f.	Patsari	Fabaceae	Tree	The roots are used in syphilis
44	<i>Dioscorea bulbifera</i> L.	Karukanadha	Dioscoreaceae	Climbing herb	Leaf paste applied to heal wounds
45	<i>Dioscorea oppositifolia</i> L.	Aretega	Dioscoreaceae	Twinning	Leaf decoction is taken orally to remove gallbladder stones
46	<i>Dracaena roxburghiana</i> (Schult. & Schult.f.) Byng & Christenh.	Kittalanara	Asperagaceae	Fleshy herb	Leaves are pounded and the pulp is made into a bandage to bind the broken bones

47	<i>Ecbalium viride</i> (Forssk.) Alston	Nilathemada	Acanthaceae	Small shrub	leaf juice applied as an antidote to scorpion sting
48	<i>Elephantopus scaber</i> L.	Garugujji	Asteraceae	Perennial herb	Decoction of the roots are taken to prevent leucorrhoea
49	<i>Entada pursaetha</i> DC.	Tikkativva	Fabaceae	Climber	The roots are used to cure hydrophobia
50	<i>Ficus racemosa</i> L.	Medichettu	Moraceae	Tree	Fruit paste is applied to heal foot cracks
51	<i>Ficus religiosa</i> L.	Ravichettu	Moraceae	Tree	Bark decoction used in bathing to heal skin diseases
52	<i>Globba marantina</i> L.	Chilakamukku	Zingiberaceae	Herb	Plant paste is used as emollient for poultices for wounds
53	<i>Glycosmis pentaphylla</i> (Retz.) DC.	Golugu	Rutaceae	Shrub	The ripe fruit is taken to improve cartilage tissue
54	<i>Gmelina arborea</i> Roxb. ex Sm.	Gummadi	Lamiaceae	Tree	Seed paste is applied to heal carbuncles
55	<i>Grona triflora</i> (L.) H. Ohashi & K. Ohashi	Muntamandu	Fabaceae	Herb	The decoction of leaves is used to cure dysentery
56	<i>Guilandina bonduc</i> L.	Gacchaku	Fabaceae	Perennial shrub	Seed powder is used to cure Prostate cancer
57	<i>Adina cordifolia</i> (Roxb.) Brandis	Kamba	Rubiaceae	Tree	Pounded leaves are used as a poultice for burns
58	<i>Helicteres isora</i> L.	Potra	Malvaceae	Shrub	Leaf extraction is used to treat eye infections.
59	<i>Hellenia speciosa</i> (J.Koenig) S.R.Dutta	Bogachikadumpa	Costaceae	Tuberous herb	Rhizome decoction taken to cure hysteria
60	<i>Holarrhena pubescens</i> Wall. Ex G. Don	Palankudu	Apocynaceae	Small tree	Bark of the plant is used for dysentery
61	<i>Ichnocarpus frutescens</i> (L.) W.T. Aiton	Karrativva	Apocynaceae	Climbing shrub	Flower paste applied to restore skin
62	<i>Ixora pavetta</i> Andrews	Korivichettu	Rubiaceae	Shrub	Roots are said to be used against snake bites
63	<i>Jatropha curcas</i> L.	Nepalam	Euphorbiaceae	Shrub	The juice of the plant is used in scabies.
64	<i>Jatropha gossypifolia</i> L.	Vathanarayanaku	Euphorbiaceae	Shrub	Seed oil is applied externally to cure pruritus
65	<i>Justicia adhatoda</i> L.	Addasaramu	Acanthaceae	Shrub	The extract of leaves are used as cough remedy
66	<i>Lannea coromandelica</i> (Houtt.) Merr.	Gumpena	Anacardiaceae	Tree	The bark powder mixed with sheep milk is used to treat otomycosis
67	<i>Leea indica</i> (Burm.f.) Merr.	Jatamakuti	Leeaceae	Shrub	Two drops of leaf decoction poured in ear to overcome vertigo problem
68	<i>Leucas aspera</i> (Willd.) Link	Tellathummi	Lamiaceae	Herb	Plant decoction used against malaria

69	<i>Leucas cephalotes</i> (Roth) Spreng.	Tummi	Lamiaceae	Herb	Leaf extraction is used for dyspepsia
70	<i>Mallotus philippensis</i> (Lam.) Mull.Arg.	Sindhura kaya	Euphorbiaceae	Tree	Seed powder is used to treat urinary infections
71	<i>Mangifera indica</i> L.	Mamidi	Anacardiaceae	Tree	Leaf paste applied to heal psoriasis
72	<i>Mimosa pudica</i> L.	Matramullu	Fabaceae	Under shrub	Plant ash is used to clear mouth ulcers
73	<i>Paramollugo nudicaulis</i> (Lam.) Thulin	Paripatta	Molluginaceae	Herb	Leaf juice is gargled to prevent Tonsillitis
74	<i>Mucuna pruriens</i> (L.) DC.	PeddaDulagondi	Fabaceae	climber	Boiled seed paste is applied to reduce arthritis
75	<i>Naringi crenulata</i> (Roxb.) Nicolson	Tunivelaga	Rutaceae	Small tree	Leaf paste heals infectious skin diseases
76	<i>Ocimum basilicum</i> L.	Bhutulasi	Lamiaceae	Herb	Leaf juice is used for diarrhoea
77	<i>Pavetta indica</i> L.	Papidi	Rubiaceae	Shrub	The root boiled in mustard oil, it is used to reduce body swelling
78	<i>Phanera vahlii</i> (Wight & Arn.) Benth.	Addaku	Fabaceae	Climbing shrub	Bark powder taken with water for curing dysentery
79	<i>Pithecellobium dulce</i> (Roxb.) Benth.	Simachintha	Fabaceae	Tree	Seed powder is used to treat urinary infections
80	<i>Pleurolobus gangeticus</i> (L.) J.St.-Hil. ex H.Ohashi & K.Ohashi	Kolapannu	Fabaceae	Under shrub	The root is useful in chronic fevers
81	<i>Monoon longifolia</i> (Sonn.) B.Xue & R.M.K.Saunders	Naramamidi	Annonaceae	Tree	Seed powder mixed with <i>Jeera</i> is taken orally for gonorrhoea
82	<i>Pterospermum xylocarpum</i> (Gaertn.) Oken	Thadachettu	Malvaceae	Small tree	Bandage of crushed leaves on the knee to reduces swelling
83	<i>Pupalia lappacea</i> (L.) Juss.	Antintha	Amaranthaceae	Under shrub	Entire plant paste applied to cure Ringworm
84	<i>Pyrrosia adnascens</i> (Sw.) Ching	Namminaluka	Polypodiaceae	Epiphytic fern	Leaf paste is used to heal sprains
85	<i>Rauvolfia serpentina</i> (L.) Benth. ex Kurz	Pathalagirada	Apocynaceae	Under shrub	The roots are used in the treatment of insanity
86	<i>Rauvolfia tetraphylla</i> L.	Papitigaruda	Apocynaceae	Under shrub	Root paste is applied as an antidote for bee's venom

87	<i>Schleichera oleosa</i> (Lour.) Oken	Pullakaya	Sapindaceae	Tree	Fruit is taken to cure peptic ulcers
88	<i>Senna obtusifolia</i> (L.) H.S.Irwin & Barneby	Thuntem	Fabaceae	Herb	Root decoction is used to relieve abdominal pain
89	<i>Shorea robusta</i> C.F.Gaertn.	Guggilam	Dipterocarpaceae	large Tree	Dried gum mixed with coconut oil is applied to heal psoriasis
90	<i>Cleome rutidosperma</i> DC.	Kukkasarasavalu	Cleomaceae	Herb	Burned seed fumes are inhaled to cure migraine
91	<i>Smilax zeylanica</i> L.	Phirangibaddu	Smilacaceae	climber	Root paste is applied to heal wounds in cattle
92	<i>Stachytarpheta jamaicensis</i> (L.) Vahl	Kellavasa	Asteraceae	Herb	Leaf decoction is given to cure bronchitis in children
93	<i>Streblus asper</i> Lour.	Barnika	Moraceae	Small tree	Stem bark decoction cures recurrent fever
94	<i>Strychnos nux-vomica</i> L.	Mushidiak	Loganiaceae	Tree	Seed powder used to treat mental condition
95	<i>Terminalia arjuna</i> (Roxb. ex DC.) Wight & Arn.	Tellamaddi	Combretaceae	Tree	Stem bark decoction is used as heart tonic
96	<i>Terminalia bellirica</i> (Gaertn.) Roxb.	Tanikaya	Combretaceae	Tree	Fruit decoction is used to bronchitis
97	<i>Terminalia chebula</i> Retz.	Karakkaichettu	Combretaceae	Moderate sized tree	Dried fruit powder is used as purgative
98	<i>Tinospora cordifolia</i> (Willd.) Hook.f. & Thomson	Tippatiga	Menispermaceae	Shrubby climber	Stem decoction is taken to control high blood pressure
99	<i>Trichodesma indicum</i> (L.) Sm.	Ulavakalupu	Boraginaceae	Herb	The roots are made into paste and applied to reduce joint pains
100	<i>Trichodesma africanum</i> (L.) Sm.	Kondapotla	Cucurbitaceae	Climber	Leaf decoction with <i>Jeera</i> powder is taken orally for bilious disorders
101	<i>Triumfetta rhomboidea</i> Jacq.	Chirusitrika	Malvaceae	Undershrub	Leaves are used to clear indigestion in cattle
102	<i>Vachellia leucophloea</i> (Roxb.) Maslin, Seigler & Ebinger	Tellatamma	Fabaceae	Small tree	Stem bark powder is used to cure oral ulcers
103	<i>Vanda tessellata</i>	Saga	Orchidaceae	Epiphytic herb	Velamen root paste is applied to heal bone fracture
104	<i>Vitex negundo</i> L.	Vavila	Lamiaceae	Small tree	Postpartum complications are prevented by bathing in boiled water of the leaves
105	<i>Vitex altissima</i> L.f.	Busichettu	Lamiaceae	Tree	Leaf paste is used for Lichen planus skin disease

106	<i>Zingiber capitatum</i> Roxb.	Karupasupu	Zingiberaceae	Tuberous herb	Rhizome decoction is taken for curing fevers
107	<i>Zingiber roseum</i> (Roxb.) Roscoe	Rajulaallum	Zingiberaceae	Tuberous herb	Rhizome paste is used for stomach-ache

Table 2: Family-wise utility of ethnomedicinal plant taxa

Rank	No. of Plant Taxa	No. of Families	Family/Families
1	14	1	Fabaceae
2	6	1	Lamiaceae
3	5	2	Apocynaceae, Asteraceae
4	4	5	Amaranthaceae, Malvaceae, Moraceae, Rutaceae, Zingiberaceae
5	3	5	Annonaceae, Combretaceae, Euphorbiaceae, Poaceae, Rubiaceae
6	2	10	Acanthaceae, Anacardiaceae, Araceae, Aristolochiaceae, Asperagaceae, Boraginaceae, Cucurbitaceae, Dioscoreaceae,

Note: The remaining 22 families (Table 1) are represented by one species each.

Figure 1: Growth-form pattern of ethnomedicinal plants

Figure:2 Percentage of Organoleptic part used in medicine

CONCLUSION

Information collected has revealed that 107 plant species are used by the tribes lived in and around Donubai *Sal* patch. These interesting plant species having not only medicinal importance, but also contribute significantly to the floristic diversity of the area. The tribal people are playing a vital role in protecting the natural *sal* patch from illicit felling, smuggling and from fire incidents. This practice helps to conserve natural habitat and medicinal plants. Sunnapugedda waterfall, which attracts tourists, is located very near to this *sal* patch. Hence many people are visiting this place as a picnic spot during the winter season. In this context, valuable plants become rare due to dumping plastic wastes, taking away the interested plants and stampeding the natural vegetation.

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